

Nahal Mishmar cave

also known as “Scouts Cave”, “Cave of the Treasure”, “Nahal Mishmar hoard”

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Entry tags: Levantine Religion, Syro-Palestinian Religion, Religious Place, Nature worship, Religious Group, Natural Religion, Tomb

Located in the Judean Desert on the west side of the Dead Sea, the Nahal Mishmar Cave, or Cave of the Treasure, have played a significant role in discussions on Chalcolithic religion and cult in the southern Levant. The cave is renowned for its cache of over 400 lost-wax-cast copper objects, which included mace heads, scepters and standards, weapons and tools, as well as cult objects carved from hippopotamus and elephant ivory, beads of imported and local stone, and a domestic assemblage. Iconographically, objects in the hoard reflect the sharing of motifs on other ritual objects such as cult stands, ceramic ossuaries, and metal standards found in other burial cave assemblages throughout the southern Levant. Regarding the dating of the hoard and the period of its deposition, the objects were placed under a reed mat whose radiocarbon dates returned results ranging from 4350-3500 BCE, leading to debate on when the hoard was deposited and by whom. Additionally, ceramic sherds dated to the EB IB demonstrate reoccupation of the cave during the late fourth millennium, further complicating the picture. Analysis of some of the copper objects reveals the metal was both local, possibly from the Feinan region, as well as imported from much further abroad, reflecting far-reaching exchange networks. Both the production techniques employed to cast the tools and ceremonial objects and the objects themselves find parallels in the Beersheba settlements, which has led some to propose a Ghassulian connection while others reject such proposals. Given the wealth in material, the cultic nature of the objects, and the proximity to En Gedi, David Ussishkin advocated for a connection to the cultic shrine 10 km south of the cave; other scholars debate this proposal in favor of a range of other possibilities. Nevertheless, the cave and the hoard have come to play a role in the study of Chalcolithic religion.

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3100 BCE

Region: Judean desert

Region tags: Judean Desert

Nahal Mishmar cave west of the Dead Sea in the Judean desert

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bar-Adon, Pessah. 1980. The Cave of the Treasure: The Finds from the Caves in Nahal Mishmar. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society.

– Source 2: Ilan, David, and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171-194.

– Source 3: Shalem, Dina. 2015. "Motifs on the Nahal Mishmar Hoard and the Ossuaries: Comparative Observations and Interpretations." *Journal of the Israel Prehistoric Society* 45:217-237.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.imj.org.il/en/collections/197941>

– Source 1 Description: Israel Museum collection of artifacts from the Cave of the Treasure

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960-1961

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Expedition to the Judean Desert

Notes: Bar-Adon, P. 1961. "Expedition C." *Israel Exploration Journal* 11 (1/2):25-35. Bar-Adon, P. 1962. "Expedition C—The Cave of the Treasure." *Israel Exploration Journal* 12 (3/4):215-226. Bar-Adon, Pessah. 1980. *The Cave of the Treasure: The Finds from the Caves in Nahal Mishmar*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Cave

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Type of elevation

– Rock face

Notes: The entrance to the cave is 200m above the southern bank of Nahal Mishmar and 50 m below the top of the cliff (Bar-Adon 1961, 25)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: Although it should be noted that caves in the region could have been used as temporary domestic habitations

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: Cave

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE
Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE
Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE
Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: The function of the cave is debated. Burials are present in addition to the hoard, as well as domestic wares suggesting the cave was multifunctional

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE
Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE
Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4350 BCE - 3200 BCE

Region: Nahal Mishmar cave

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

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Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: The cave is natural and thus could not have been built by a specific group of people. However, it was utilized by a specific group of people, or groups of people over time.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: There is not enough information to indicate the motivation behind the establishment of the cave as a burial. Ilan and Rowan (2015) argue the cave formed one of many in the Judean Desert that may have been a necropolis.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably the stones in the cave were local to the region

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest the cave was decorated

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The cave is best known for the hoard of objects found hidden in a crevice in the cave, covered with a reed mat and large stone. As such, the following section captures the iconography of the hoard—not the cave

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: A human face is modeled on a copper scepter (Bar-Adon 1980: No. 21) and eyes appear on two other copper models (Bar-Adon 1980: Nos. 9 and 151). The combination of round eyes and a prominent nose is an iconographic motif that becomes widespread during the Chalcolithic, appearing on ossuaries, cult stands, and ceramic vessels (Shalem 2015:282).

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Several standards include zoomorphic depictions of caprids and birds; whether these were considered supernatural is unknown

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: The depiction of a human face appears on a copper scepter (Bar-Anon 1980: No. 21). These features were also incorporated into a cast copper cylindrical object

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The Nahal Mishmar cave with the hoard found in it forms one of several caves with 20 total burials in the region (Bar Adon 1980). Five burials were found in the Nahal Mishmar cave, however the date of the burials in the cave are debated by some scholars (e.g., Gilead and Gošić 2015). However, when one looks to the use of the Judean Desert more broadly, it has been argued the landscape served as a Chalcolithic necropolis with the En Gedi cultic complex functioning as a mortuary shrine (Ilan and Rowan 2015). The arrangement of a mortuary shrine and necropolis on the West Bank of the Dead Sea was also proposed to parallel the later Nile Valley funerary practices centered on the west of the Nile as the place of the setting sun (Ilan and Rowan 2015).

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say for certain that the site was a place for the worship of the dead. The association of the hoard with burials in the cave led some scholars to propose the hoard functioned as funerary offerings (e.g., Ilan 1994).

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: There is nothing to suggest that the cave served as a place for the treatment of the corpse. However, David Ilan and Yorke Rowan (2015) have proposed the cave should be viewed in the broader landscape, which they argue was a Chalcolithic necropolis. Within the Judean Desert landscape, they raise the possibility that the treatment of corpses took place at the En Gedi shrine/cultic complex (Ilan and Rowan 2015:186-187).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of the evidence is such that we cannot say whether the burials in the tomb were co-sacrifices

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear whether the hoard was connected to the burials in the cave. However, the sheer amount of copper—from both local and foreign sources—is representative of significant value as many resources went into producing the objects in the hoard

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to say whether the burials in the cave were related by blood. The Chalcolithic period appears to be a time when subterranean spaces for the interment of the dead became a standard practice. In the Judean Desert, it appears primary burial in caves was the dominant mode of mortuary practice (Rowan and Ilan 2015).

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: Dated to the Chalcolithic, Level III contained evidence of domestic habitation in the form of food preparation, weaving and spinning. However, the date of the burials is debated. Yorke Rowan and David Ilan (2015:94-95) have argued at least one of the five burials is contemporary with Chalcolithic domestic refuse.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to state whether supernatural monitoring was present

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While domestic refuse dating to the Chalcolithic and EB IB was identified in this cave, there is nothing to indicate a dedicated living space for religious specialists. However, it is possible that religious specialists temporarily inhabited the space but there is no dedicated space set aside for such individuals.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There is nothing to indicate this was a space for training religious specialists

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The concentration of cast copper objects is significant as it reflects hoarding of a rare, socially valued material during the fifth and fourth millennium BCE. However, it is not clear whether the community responsible for the hoard's deposition controlled access to and distribution of this material.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of burials in the cave—the date of which remains debated (Gilead and Gošić 2015) —paired with a recent proposal the Judean Desert formed a Chalcolithic necropolis (Ilan and Rowan 2015) suggests the region was a place for certain communities to bury their dead. Presumably rituals related to rites of passage were enacted in these spaces, and thus one might argue the location was where burial services were provided to the community. Mortuary rituals in subterranean spaces do appear as a new practice in Chalcolithic ritual (Rowan and Ilan 2015).

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: Nissim Amzallag (2018; 2019) proposed numerous cast copper objects in the hoard reflect a visual code of communication comprising icons meant to be "read" through the rebus principle—a type of proto writing. According to this proposal, the messages encoded in these symbols passed on secret knowledge related to metallurgical processes and in this way is connected to the religious beliefs of the Ghassulian community responsible for the hoard's casting. This proposal was rejected by Aren Wilson-Wright (2020) for two reasons: 1) we simply do not know what language the people spoke who were responsible for the production of the Nahal Mishmar hoard; and 2) based on what is known of

Semitic during the 5th and 4th millennium BCE, the rebuses proposed by Amzallag cannot be not valid. While Amzallag's proposal accepts a late 5th millennium BCE date for the hoard's deposition, Nadia Ben-Marzouk (2020: 319-352; 2021) has argued for a late fourth millennium BCE date of deposition, and that numerous symbols in the hoard reflect symbols of power associated with communities from the Nile Valley and Delta (see also Gates 1992). A late fourth millennium BCE date for the hoard's final deposition is contemporary with the emergence of writing in both Egypt and Mesopotamia and thus several objects in the hoard could have served as the inspiration for several Egyptian logograms.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Nahal Mishmar cave, Bar-Adon, Pessah. *The Cave of the Treasure: The Finds from the Caves in Nahal Mishmar*. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society, 1980.

Reference: Nahal Mishmar cave, Ilan, David, and Yorke Rowan. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis". *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28, no. 2 (2015): 171-94.

Reference: Nahal Mishmar cave, Shalem, Dina. "Motifs on the Nahal Mishmar Hoard and the Ossuaries: Comparative Observations and Interpretations". *Journal of the Israel Prehistoric Society* 45 (2015): 217-37.